

Fully 3D Printed Spring Powered Car: A Project-Based Learning Experience

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Abstract

Since its introduction more than three decades ago, additive manufacturing (AM) has gained popularity and has become one important technology in supporting the revolution of the new industrial era. Being familiar with AM, therefore, opens up more opportunities for graduates as the technology will be available more and more in all types of businesses. Consequently, a course on AM has become a regular part of engineering curricula, including the Additive Manufacturing and Reverse Engineering course offered in the Industrial and Manufacturing Engineering Program at the Asian Institute of Technology. This course contains several activities that require student engagement, and as a part of competence development, the students are always assigned a group project. All groups are usually encouraged to explore their interests under a given common theme. Presented in this paper is our project-based learning experience from this group project activity. For our class, we were asked to design and build an interesting artefact that is required physical assembly of printed components. Our group decided to make a movable toy car that all parts, such as gears, wheels, and body frames, were printed from Polylactic Acid (PLA) filaments. It is worth mentioning that printing a functional spring was quite a challenge. This paper will share our journey from brainstorming to design, to parameter identification until testing the final product. Challenges encountered along the journey and our way of overcoming these challenges are also discussed.

Keywords: Additive Manufacturing, 3D printing, PBL, Project.

1 Introduction

Additive manufacturing (AM) technology has become integral to modern prototyping and manufacturing. AM technology is the term used for the technology that builds three-dimensional objects by adding layers of materials such as plastic, wood, concrete, or metal. It includes subsets such as rapid prototyping, 3D printing, direct digital manufacturing, layered manufacturing, and additive fabrication. AM provides cost and time-saving ways to produce low-volume and customized products with complicated geometries and advanced material properties and functionality (Huang, Y., Leu, M. C., Mazumder, J., & Donmez, A, 2015).

There are different categories that comprise additive manufacturing technology. All AM systems can be easily categorized into liquid-based, solid-based, and powder-based. In a Liquid-based RP system, a liquid state is the initial form of the material. Through a curing process, the liquid is transformed into a solid-state. For example, 3D Systems' Stereolithography Apparatus (SLA), Cubital's Solid Ground Curing (SGC). Solid-based RP systems are meant to encompass all forms of material in the solid-state except for powder. In this condition, the solid form can include the shape in the form of a wire, a roll, laminates, and pellets. For instance, Cubic Technologies' Laminated Object Manufacturing (LOM), Stratasys' Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM). In a strict sense, the powder is somehow created to be in a solid-state. However, it is intentionally made as a category outside the solid-based RP systems to mean powder in grain-like form. For example, 3D System's Selective Laser Sintering (SLS), Z Corporation's Three-Dimensional Printing (3DP) (Chua, C. K., Leong, K. F., & Lim, C. S, 2010).

A course on AM has become a regular part of engineering curricula, including the Additive Manufacturing and Reverse Engineering course offered in the Industrial and Manufacturing Engineering Program at the Asian Institute of Technology. Based on project-based learning, this course contains several activities that require student engagement, and as a part of competence development, the students are always assigned a group project. Problem-based learning (PBL) is a team-based teaching and learning approach that uses "real life" problems to help students gain technical knowledge and develop important skill sets in problem-solving, collaborative engagements, effective communication, and research. In PBL, students are presented with an

example of a real-life situation and are expected to analyse and/or propose solutions or courses of action which they can then optimize (Tang, Y. M., & Mo, J. P, 2015).

PBL develops cognitive skills associated with problem-solving, group processing skills, and reflective and evaluative skills as well as developing theoretical understanding. As students reflect on the problem-based experience, they acquire transferable skills and knowledge which equip them with the ability to approach a range of novel situations likely to be encountered in their professional careers. Student satisfaction indicators and industry engagement indicators are high. Problem-based learning approaches are commonly applied in science subjects. The analysis of the effect of the Problem based Learning Method in the success degree and motivation of students showed that the problem-based learning method made a positive contribution to the students' success (Ergül, N. R., & Kargın, E. K, 2014).

In this paper, we propose a problem-based learning approach to teach the Additive Manufacturing and Reverse Engineering course. The learning process is designed to conform to well-known principles in the Additive Manufacturing course as well as taking full advantage of the latest 3D printing. This paper will share our journey from brainstorming to design, to parameter identification until testing the final product. Challenges encountered along the journey and our way of overcoming these challenges are also discussed.

2 The process of Additive Manufacturing

The generic AM process includes the following steps.

Step 1: Computer-aided design (CAD); Products developed through AM are created beginning with a software model containing the exterior geometry. Another viable option is to reverse engineer an item or part using a laser or scanning device.

Step 2: Conversion to STL; This step requires converting files to STL, which is the current standard and can be produced by a majority of CAD systems. The STL file is required because it contains the dimensions of the closed exterior surface and is necessary to calculate the layers.

Step 3: STL File Manipulation and Upload to AM Machines; The generated STL file is uploaded to the AM machine. Necessary manipulation of the file may be performed at this time to ensure details such as size, position, and angle.

Step 4: 3D Printer/Machine Setup; Configure the AM machine setting to ensure it accounts for restrictions, power source, layer width, precision degrees, timing, and other configurations.

Step 5: Build; The AM machine builds the object via an automated process similar to paper printers. Limited oversight needs are required to make sure the printer has adequate material and to address possible software malfunctions.

Step 6: Removal; The printed object must be removed upon completion of build. Aside from simply removing it, safety interlocks in place to prevent the printer from overheating or from moving parts.

Step 7: Post Processing; Depending on the removal of the printed object from the printer, it may need to be cleaned, subjected, or unbraced to final manual touch-ups.

Step 8: Application; The 3D-printed object may now be functional. In some cases, it may require additional manipulation such as priming, painting, texturing, or finishing necessary to realize the final intended end-use state. At this point, it can be used or assembled into the component of which it is a part for complete functionality.

3 Our Learning Environment

For the first time that we started learning this course, we felt that the teaching method is different from other courses because the instructor gave the lecture for only one-third of the section and the remainder included the group assignments and activities. Sometimes, the instructor made us into three groups and gave different

titles related to the AM course and let us access the knowledge and we had to share and explain what we had learned and known. At that time, it was difficult to get this learning flow, but later we got used to it. Figure 1 is our learning environment called AM Space.

Figure 1. Our AM Space

The first time, we got to the AM Space, we were surprised because there were a lot of 3D printers and we were having access to use them. We got a chance to explore innovative ideas to design functions of the 3D printing products. 3D printers in our laboratory are "Flashforge Adventure 3", fused decomposition modeling (FDM). We were very excited to collaborate on lectures and practical activities. Since there was enough equipment for all of us, every student had access to use freely.

4 Our Group's Project

Since this AM course is project-based learning, we were asked to perform as a group and to make a project related to 3D printing. Therefore, our class members were separated into three groups, each group containing three members. Each group had to come out with their own ideas and discuss their activities related to their ideas. Initially, our group wanted to make a movable car with some electronic components, motors, and battery until we started to questioning ourselves why we cannot make a fully 3D printed movable car without any electronic components. On the other hand, making a 3D model and printing a solid object without any characteristics were too simple and easy. So, our group decided to make something special that has some features with elasticity and flexibility using only PLA filament. Based on the FDM printing process, our group was keen on making a movable car with components that were all printed with PLA filaments. In order to make a movable car, spring plays an essential part and at the same time, it was difficult to print with a normal 3D printer. Thus, making a fully 3D printed movable car became our group's challenge. It is worth mentioning that printing a functional spring was quite a challenge. Finally, our group decided to set the following goals.

- To analyse the capabilities of the 3D printers that we got from the lab.
- To design the elastic print parts with the PLA filament.
- To discuss and design on the CAD Design of the fully 3D printed movable car.

In this AM course, the instructor also gave the guidelines of how to handle 3D printers. Moreover, we learned some important factors of 3D printers' manufacturing capabilities. They are as follows.

4.1 Materials

In FDM printing process, we learned some common materials used in the 3D printers like thermoplastic materials, Polylactic acid (PLA), Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), polycarbonate (PC) and Polyamides (nylon). At that time, we could use only thermoplastics (PLA) materials for our group project.

4.2 Size and accuracy

The size of the designed parts depends on the dimension of 3D printers. The maximum print volume of the 3D printers was 150 mm on both X, Y, and Z axes. On the other hand, the manufacturing time is affected by the size of the product. As a result, printing time has also needed to be taken into consideration during the design of the parts.

4.3 Feature design

The printer's nozzle tip was 0.4 mm. The resolution of the printing part can be affected by the nozzle size. The printing time also depends on the diameter of the nozzle. For example, if the nozzle diameter is large, the extrusion width becomes larger and it will decrease the printing time. On the other hand, normally large nozzles cannot print the small parts that are smaller than the nozzle. Printing with support is required when plastic must be deposited on a layer where there is insufficient plastic on the previous layer. Support printing and removal processes are usually time-consuming. The use of support is also wasteful and increases unnecessary costs.

Figure 2. 3D scanning and exporting STL files

Furthermore, in our class, we got a chance to learn 3D scanning as shown in Figure 2 thoroughly which is a process of analysing an object from the real world, to collect all the data in order to recreate its shapes and appearance, digitally. It is useful for the 3D printing process because 3D printers need STL format files which 3D scanning generates.

5 Our Group Project Experiences

For our group, all members were keen on making a movable car with components that were all printed using PLA filament. A lot of discussions and plans were conducted to achieve the goals and challenges. In order to make a movable car, spring plays an essential part, and at the same time, it was difficult to print with a normal 3D printer. Moreover, as our car needed to combine serial parts such as gears, wheels and body frames, the CAD designs of the car came to play an important issue to consider. For the slicing software, we used the "Flash Print" slicing software. Printing parameters like shell parameters, scale, infill density, and layer height affected significantly on assembly components.

5.1 Printing and testing the elastic and flexible objects

In order to make the printing parts flexible and elastic, our group discussed and designed three parts; band, compression spring, and conical spring. Also, PLA material was used in the FDM printing process. Figure 3 shows the 3D Printed band, compression spring, and conical spring.

5.1.1 Band

The first design of the band was simple but the parameter of the shell and extrusion width should be in the correct ratio in order to generate an efficient printing process that is the ratio of the thickness of the print part and the extrusion width. We faced some problems in the printing process that were the poor resolution of the print parts because the printing path was not a single line and continuous. Instead, it should be a single line in each layer and we decided to make the printing path continuous to get a good resolution product and the printed part elastic and flexible.

5.1.2 Compression spring

The second one was a compression spring. It was difficult to print with our 3D printers. Normally, the design of the print part needs a support structure. On the other hand, if we added support structures or placed another position, the spring would not be elastic and flexible. So, our group discussed and made the tests by changing the parameters of the printing setting. Finally, we got the correct setting and a compression spring. This proved that our printers have some limitations but are still powerful.

5.1.3 Conical spring

The conical spring played a key role in making the car movable. In the printing process, there was almost no error however we found many Spidey strings in the printed part. This effect was caused because the retraction parameter was small. The retraction parameter is the length of the recoil movement of the filament necessary to prevent dripping of material during movements and displacements that the extruder performs during printing. To solve this problem, we could set the retraction parameter from the slicing software.

Figure 3. 3D Printed band, compression spring and conical spring

5.2 Testing shrinkage effect

There were many things that go on during the 3D printing process. There were times where shrinkage was not generally an issue and other times when it could be a big deal. When the size of the object was crucial, material shrinkage could become more of a problem and must be taken more seriously. In order to do assembly, we needed to consider the shrinkage effect of the PLA material. This shrinkage was a direct result of the transition from a liquid to a solid-state during the curing process. Depending on the material, there could also be an increase in shrinkage based on the temperature of the environment. First, we designed two cylindrical shapes as shown in figure (4) and we put a gap between them to get a smooth rotation between the body frame and gears. So, we had to check the gap which is appropriate for fitting and smooth assembly. Then, we printed four sets to test the appropriate gap for our car. Depending on the test result, we decided a 0.3 mm gap for fitting parts and a 0.5 mm gap for smooth parts. In this testing, we found that the bottom of the printed part was a little bigger than the upper part as seen in the yellow circles in Figure 4. We decided that it was the elephant foot effect and we could neglect that effect because all print parts needed the correct dimension only at the upper portion.

Figure 4. CAD design and testing shrinkage effect

5.3 CAD Design

In order to fulfil the third objective, our team discussed and designed a CAD model of the toy car. We discussed some features that our product can be printed easily, our print parts don't need support structures, minimize the number of parts to print, and to make our product more realistic. We designed a total of 12 parts including body frame left and right, spring, main gear, gear locker, secondary gear, axel gear, axles for front and rear, wheels, tires, spacer and key, and some of them are shown in Figure 5. For the main body frame, we designed to get the maximum print volume of the printer because it was the biggest part of our car.

Figure 5. Some Components of CAD Design

5.4 Printing Process

In the printing process, there were many factors and parameters to consider. Our group focused on the printing temperature, layer height, shell parameters, and infill density. Moreover, the filament was the major requirement. In this project, our team used PLA material. According to the brands, the printing temperatures of the PLA filament were different ranging from 190°C to 220°C. And we also had to consider the print bed temperature because our 3D printers had heated print beds. The print bed temperature was ranging from 40°C to 60°C depending on the room temperature and printed volume. Other factors like layer height, shell parameters, and infill density were considered according to the required print parts. To print a toy car, the components were divided into four groups according to the printing setting.

- Customize shell parameter printing setting
- Customize infill density printing setting
- Multi-colour printing setting
- Normal printing setting

5.4.1 Customize shell parameter printing setting

In our project, the gears (main, secondary and axle) needed to be strong enough but in order to save material and time, our team decided not to increase the infill density but to increase the shell count parameter. For a normal printing setting, the shell count perimeter is normally 2. For our gears, our team printed with standard resolution (0.27 mm layer height), standard infill (15%) and shell count parameter 4 for accuracy and long-lasting gear teeth.

5.4.2 Customize infill density printing setting

Our team printed the main parts of our project which were spring for controlling the movement of the main gear and gear locker that acts as the interface between gear and spring. We had to print both of them with infill 100% and shell count parameter 4 because it was important to have no gap inside the print parts to have good strength for resistance to tension.

5.4.3 Multi-colour printing setting

In order to make a realistic car, the multi-colour printing was also important. On the other hand, we faced some material limitations as one colour was not available enough. Therefore, our team decided to choose the multi-colour printing process involving black, white and red. According to this issue, some parts such as spring, gears and axle were not much important in colour choices, however, the main importance was the car body frames, wheels and tires. For this printing process, we set the required height of the print part, make the printer pause, reloaded the required colour of the filament and resumed the printer again. Finally, we got a colourful body frame as seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6. 3D printing process of some components

5.4.4 Normal printing setting

The rest of the parts, wheels, tires, front and rear axles and spacer were printed with normal printing setting; layer height 0.27 mm, infill 15%, shell parameter 2.

5.5 Problems and Errors in Printing Process

After we designed and printed the parts out, they made some errors. As illustrated in Figure 7, the first parts broke easily because of infill density. It just only had a 10% infill. The second one was 100% infill however, it

still broke because the load of the spring was too strong. The reason behind the break of the third part was the insufficiency of the shell count parameter. The fourth part had some rough surface in the first layer and the last part had a problem with layer shifting where layers of the printed object were shifted from their intended positions. Getting rough surfaces and layer shifting in the printing process was because of the bad calibration that was measuring the distance between the nozzle tip and the print bed.

Figure 7. Problems and errors in printing process

5.6 Finishing and Assembly

In most cases, the quality of 3D printed models does not meet the user's particular requirements. In such cases, additional finishing by blasting, sanding, varnishing, and so on is required. Finishing has to be done in any case but it is not an entire element of the AM process. In our project, we tried to design our parts to their best not to require a finishing process.

There were two parts in the assembly process, first model assembly, and final product assembly. Figure 8 displays the components of the final product before making assembly.

Figure 8. On the way to final product

5.7.1 First Model

The white car in Figure 9 is our first model. The gaps between body frame and gears were not smooth enough, and for the strength of the body frame that we can see, some parts broke accidentally as shown in the yellow circle. It broke because of insufficient infill density and shell count parameters as we mentioned above.

5.7.2 Final Product

Learning from the experiences from the first model, we made some improvements to get the most satisfying result of our product. The gears could rotate correctly and the spring could perform well. The assembly process got easier and It could be done within 2 minutes because of the dimension parameters and printing setting. Moreover, in our final model, we did not need to make additional finishing processes.

Figure 9. Assembly process

6 Result and Testing

The red car illustrated in Figure 9 was our final model and it was easy to print, and easy to assembly within 2 minutes. Then we added the multi colours in the main body frame. For this car, it took 27 hours to print out. But it also had drawbacks. We encountered that the rear wheel tires can slip easily. So, we managed the rubber band for the rear wheels to prevent the car from slipping. Moreover, our model was designed to meet the maximum size of the build plate. At the same time, printers in our AM space are not big enough to print out all parts together. That's why we had to print the parts separately in a consequent manner. Furthermore, it was also made only for short way drives. Eventually, our final product met our satisfaction of easy to print and assembly, realistic, movable, and the most important, having an elastic and flexible spring.

7 Conclusion

The active learning method that the instructor applied in the Additive Manufacturing and Reverse Engineering course allowed us to engage more in our learning. With his teaching approach by providing a big picture and key points for each of the topics and giving us different subtopics to study, we were encouraged to explore in the team for more information and shared it with other teams. More importantly, the project-based learning in the form of the group project allowed us to work and manage as a team, to express our creativity, and to learn to handle challenges encountered. We learned to tailor individuals' ideas to obtain a group's idea. Not only to understand our idea, but we also learned to understand the capability and limitations of the machine we used. Through this learning by doing, it was not only much easier for us to understand about Additive Manufacturing than listening passively to the lectures but also stimulate our thinking and trained us to keep asking ourselves questions. This course also improves our transversal skills.

Figure 10. Our team

8 References

- Huang, Y., Leu, M. C., Mazumder, J., & Donmez, A. (2015). Additive manufacturing: current state, future potential, gaps and needs, and recommendations. *Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering*, 137(1).
- Gibson, I., Rosen, D. W., & Stucker, B. (2010). Design for additive manufacturing. In *Additive Manufacturing Technologies* (pp. 299-332). Springer, Boston, MA.
- Muniz, B. G., & Peters, K. M. (2016). *An analysis of additive manufacturing production problems and solutions*. Naval Postgraduate School Monterey United States.
- Chua, C. K., Leong, K. F., & Lim, C. S. (2010). *Rapid prototyping: principles and applications (with companion CD-ROM)*. World Scientific Publishing Company.
- Tang, Y. M., & Mo, J. P. (2015). Problem Based Learning of Systems Engineering Supported by Additive Manufacturing Processes. In *Industrial Engineering Research Special Issue of the International Conference of Technology Education (ICTE)* (Vol. 8, No. 1, pp. 77-91).
- Ergül, N. R., & Kargın, E. K. (2014). The effect of project based learning on students' science success. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 136, 537-541.